

United States Department of the Interior

FISH AND WILDLIFE SERVICE
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In Reply Refer To:
08FBDT00-2017-F-0024

APR 06 2017

Holly Costa
Acting Chief, Regulatory Division
U.S. Army Corps of Engineers
San Francisco District
1455 Market Street
San Francisco, California 94103-1398

Subject: Formal Consultation on the Alviso Pump Station Project in the City of San Jose, Santa Clara County, California (U.S. Army Corps of Engineers [Corps] file number SPN-2015-00393S)

Dear Ms. Costa:

This letter is in response to the Corps' September 9, 2016, letter requesting consultation with the U.S. Fish and Wildlife Service (Service) on the proposed Alviso Pump Station Project (project) in the City of San Jose, Santa Clara County, California. Your request was received by the Service on September 16, 2016. At issue are the proposed project's effects on the federally endangered California clapper rail (*Rallus longirostris obsoletus*)(CCR) and the endangered salt marsh harvest mouse (*Reithrodontomys raviventris*)(SMHM). This response is provided under the authority of the Endangered Species Act of 1973, as amended (16 U.S.C. 1531 *et seq.*)(Act), and in accordance with the implementing regulations pertaining to interagency cooperation (50 CFR 402).

Recent genetic analyses of rail species resulted in a change in the common name and taxonomy of the large, "clapper-type" rails (*Rallus longirostris*) of the west coast of North America to Ridgway's rail (*Rallus obsoletus*) (Maley and Brumfield 2013; Chesser *et al.* 2014). However, the change does not change the listing status of the species. The Service continues to recognize the species as the California clapper rail until the change in common name and taxonomy of the California clapper rail to Ridgway's rail is officially entered into the Federal Register.

In reviewing this project, the Service has relied upon: (1) the Corps' September 9, 2016, letter requesting consultation; (2) the May 2016 *Alviso Pump Station Biological Assessment* (BA) prepared by H.T. Harvey & Associates; (3) the March 9, 2017 supplemental electronic mail from H.T. Harvey & Associates; and (4) other information available to the Service.

The Corps determined that the project may affect and is likely to adversely affect the CCR and the SMHM. After review of the project description, the Service has determined the actions proposed to occur through implementation of the proposed project are likely to adversely affect both the CCR and SMHM. This document hereby represents the Service's biological opinion on the effects of the proposed project on the CCR and SMHM.

BIOLOGICAL OPINION

Description of the Proposed Action

The City of San Jose (City) proposes to construct a new, larger pump station and force main near the intersection of Gold and Catherine Streets. The new pump station would include a new wet well, a new standby generator, a new Master Control Center (MCC), and a new building to house those facilities.

Construction of the proposed project facilities is expected to take 6 to 8 months beginning in the summer of 2017 and likely continue into the winter of 2017. Construction work would typically occur within normal City working hours of 7 a.m. to 6 p.m. The City is proposing to conduct all construction east of the Alviso Slough levee during any time of the proposed construction timeframe. The outfall west of the Alviso Slough levee is estimated to require a minimum of ten weeks to complete and in order to meet the environmental timing constraints of California Department of Fish and Wildlife and the National Marine Fisheries Service, the City is proposing to conduct construction on the outfall west of the Alviso Slough levee from August 1 to October 15.

Typical construction equipment such as excavators, backhoes, cranes, compactors, dump trucks, front-end loaders and asphalt pavers will be utilized. Staging areas for construction materials and equipment would be located on the existing site. Access for construction will be on the existing roadways surrounding the site.

A coffer dam will be installed around the perimeter of the work area within Alviso Slough to facilitate dewatering of the work area and ensure that work is not performed within the flowing slough. Three sides of the coffer dam will be installed first with the fourth side installed at low tide when work area is driest.

Excavation and grading would be necessary for site preparation and construction of the project. Maximum excavation at the site would be approximately 25 feet for the new wet well. The finished site would be entirely paved with asphalt concrete and sloped to the bio retention troughs along Gold Street and Catherine Street between the back of the new sidewalk and the site perimeter wall.

Project Components

Pump Station Building

The new pump station will be located at the northwest corner of the site and would include piping, a wet well, pumping equipment and accessories, a standby engine generator, electrical power and control systems, and the necessary site improvements. The new building would be approximately 900 square feet in size and approximately 24 feet in height (from the finished grade at the eaves) to house the larger standby generator and MCC. The fuel storage tank for the standby generator would be located in the yard area adjacent to the new building. A concrete masonry wall would be built along the Gold Street and Catherine Street frontages. There would also be a new driveway and vehicular gate facing on each street.

Wet Well

The wet well would be approximately 68 feet in length (including the valve vault), 10 feet wide at the entrance, and approximately 28 feet wide at the back wall where the pumps will be located. The top of the wet well would be located approximately one foot above grade. The deepest part of the wet well where the pumps are to be located would be approximately 23 feet deep. The wet well will also include a trash rack before the pumps and a 30-inch recirculation pipe that will connect the pump station discharge pipe to the influent junction structure to allow testing of any one pump at a time. The wet well would be located in the southeast portion of the site and will be semi-open with railings for easy maintenance of the pumps and debris removal from the trash rack.

Force Main

A new 48-inch high density polyethylene stormwater force main would extend westward along Catherine Street to the Alviso Slough levee, where it would discharge to a new discharge structure within the river channel. The force main would exit the pump station site diagonally into Catherine Street and extend west along the north side of Catherine Street. It would pass under the Union Pacific Railroad tracks at El Dorado Street. Approaching Hope Street, the force main would cross over to the south side of the street to avoid an existing sanitary sewer line. At the west side of Hope Street, the pipe would pass through the Santa Clara Water District levee to Alviso Slough just south of the existing concrete bulkhead wall. Within the levee, the force main would extend upwards to an elevation approximately 17 feet below the top of the levee and would continue upwards to the discharge structure. The force main would have a flap gate in the discharge structure to prevent back flow in the force main.

Discharge Structure

The new discharge structure would be located in the Alviso Slough channel at the toe of the levee slope. The structure would consist of a 9-square-foot reinforced concrete box and an open top with a top elevation of 5 feet which is higher than the average high tide and which would minimize overflow of the tide into the discharge structure. Discharges would bubble up through the grating and spill onto a blanket of rock slop protection.

Conservation Measures

The City has proposed several conservation measures that are considered standard practice for construction projects. These pertain to the use of Best Management Practices while handling vehicles, fuels and other potential pollutant sources, Storm Water Pollution Prevention Plans for the protection of water quality, and the control of noxious and invasive weeds. The project BA provides further detail on these measures.

California Clapper Rail

1. Activities within 200 feet of the marsh west of Alviso Slough (from the Alviso Slough Levee east) will occur August 1 through October 15.
2. A qualified Service-approved biological monitor will conduct Worker Environmental Awareness Training for construction personnel specific to the identification of the CCR and their habitats, and notification protocols in the event that CCR are observed.

Salt Marsh Harvest Mouse

1. A qualified Service-approved biological monitor will conduct Worker Environmental Awareness Training for construction personnel specific to the identification of the SMHM and their habitats, and notification protocols in the event that SMHM are observed.
2. Prior to the start of activities within New Chicago Marsh, all herbaceous vegetation will be removed to eliminate cover for SMHM and discourage them from entering the project area. A service-approved biologist will conduct pre-construction surveys prior to vegetation removal and will monitor the removal process. Removal will start at the parking area and proceed northwards towards the open marsh. Vegetation will be removed using hand-held equipment.
3. SMHM exclusion fencing shall be installed around the primary work area and preserved vegetation within the work area to discourage SMHM from entering the project area. Every morning prior to the start of construction, the qualified Service-approved biological monitor will inspect all exclusion fences at the primary work area.
4. Where lights are installed on or around the new pump station building, they will be placed on the perimeter of the facility and directed downward and inward toward the facility roads and buildings away from the marsh. Shielding will be installed on each light to block illumination from shining upward or outward into New Chicago Marsh.

Action Area

The action area is defined as all areas to be affected directly or indirectly by the Federal action and not merely the immediate area involved in the action (50 CFR 402.02). The action area for this section 7 consultation encompasses all areas that may be directly or indirectly affected as a

result of activities for the project and the broader area that, while outside the construction zone, may be directly or indirectly affected by vibrations, noise, dust, or movement associated with the proposed project. The action area includes the project footprint and staging and access areas. After review of the BA and the project description, the Service determines that the action area consists of approximately 2.3 acres directly impacted by the construction footprint and includes those areas surrounding the construction footprint where impacts such as disturbance (e.g., areas within 700 feet for nesting and foraging CCR) may occur.

Status of Species

California Clapper Rail

The status of California clapper rail and information about its biology, ecology, distribution, and current threats is available in the *Recovery Plan for Tidal Marsh Ecosystems of Northern and Central California* (Service 2013). This document can be found at: https://www.fws.gov/sfbaydelta/documents/tidal_marsh_recovery_plan_v1.pdf. Critical habitat has not been designated for this species.

Salt Marsh Harvest Mouse

There are two subspecies of the salt marsh harvest mouse: the northern subspecies (*R. r. halicoetes*) and the southern subspecies (*R. r. raviventris*). Both subspecies are listed as endangered. The status of the salt marsh harvest mouse and information about its biology, ecology, distribution, and current threats is available in the *Recovery Plan for Tidal Marsh Ecosystems of Northern and Central California* (Service 2013). This document can be found at: https://www.fws.gov/sfbaydelta/documents/tidal_marsh_recovery_plan_v1.pdf. Critical habitat has not been designated for this species.

Environmental Baseline

Surrounding Land Uses and Existing Conditions

The project site is located in the city of San Jose in Santa Clara County, California. It is located on the northwestern edge of San Jose adjacent to the Alviso Salt Ponds and intersects Alviso Slough on the west end and the New Chicago Marsh on the east end. The majority of the project site is a paved roadway in a developed urban area with mixed residential and commercial use. A Union Pacific Railroad track passes through the project area that has been in use for many years. Train traffic occurs frequently (approximately twice per day) and creates significant noise disturbance. Both the western edge of the project that intersects Alviso Slough and the eastern edge that intersect New Chicago Marsh consist of very small strips of marsh habitat (approximately .08 acre each) and small parking areas/roads at the marsh-urban interface.

California Clapper Rail

The marsh habitats surrounding Alviso Slough support documented CCR populations and it is presumed that CCR are present within the tidal marsh complex year around. CCR are not

expected to be within the project area as there is not suitable foraging or sheltering habitat, but may be in adjacent marsh habitat west and north of the project. The Union Pacific Railroad track that parallels El Dorado Street is approximately 700 feet from the edge of the Alviso Slough tidal marsh habitat that could support CCR. Due to the frequent and extended use of the track for many years, it is likely to be considered normal background noise and any CCR that may be occupying the nearby marsh may be habituated to or avoid areas close enough to be affected by the regular noise disturbance. The Alviso Slough levee also runs along the east shoreline of Alviso Slough and stands approximately 16 feet high from the landside base. This likely poses as a physical barrier to noise and visual disturbance to the Alviso Slough tidal marsh. No suitable habitat occurs within the action area of the New Chicago marsh.

Salt Marsh Harvest Mouse

The New Chicago Marsh supports suitable habitat for the SMHM and there are documented occurrences of the SMHM in nearby marsh habitats within the larger Alviso Salt pond complex. The small strip of habitat in the action area that could support SMHM is primarily emergent tidal marsh and sparsely vegetated with pickleweed (*Salicornia pacifica*). Although this is not considered the favored habitat for the SMHM, it could provide high ground refugia during high tide events.

Effects of the Proposed Project

California Clapper Rail

Noise, vibrations, and visual disturbance from construction activities and heavy equipment may result in the harassment of individual CCR in the adjacent habitat and expose them to predation if they were flushed from cover or prevented from seeking available cover. Noise or other construction disturbance during the CCR breeding season (February 1-August 31) could result in the loss of breeding activity or nest abandonment and the loss of all eggs and chicks in the nest. The Service anticipates that construction on the east side of Alviso Slough levee will not present a visual disturbance due to the levee acting as a visual barrier nor will construction noise rise above the level that is created by the frequent train traffic and thereby constitute an adverse effect to CCR due to visual or noise disturbance. To minimize adverse effects to breeding, work within 200 feet of Alviso Slough (west of the Alviso Slough levee) is planned to occur from August 1 – through October 15. Although this is one month beyond the Service's recommended start of September 1 for the work window for the CCR's non-breeding season, the tidal marsh around Alviso Slough within 700 feet of the proposed action is a narrow strip and likely does not readily support breeding habitat for the CCR. It is also late enough in the CCR's breeding season that it is not anticipated that CCR would have nests with eggs in them and any young of the year would have likely been fledged. No work is planned to occur in the adjacent salt marsh habitat and any CCR within 700 feet of construction activities occurring on the water side of Alviso Slough levee should be able to find sufficient cover further away within the tidal marsh north of the project. The project is proposed to take approximately 6 to 8 months total in duration and work on the west side of Alviso Slough levee is anticipated to only take approximately 2 to 3 months. Although the project will result in the permanent loss of 0.02 acre and the temporary

loss of 0.01 acre of tidal marsh habitat, it is not likely that CCR would utilize the affected habitat and therefore it is not anticipated to have a noticeable effect to CCR.

Salt Marsh Harvest Mouse

Noise and vibrations from construction activities and heavy equipment may result in the harassment of individual SMHM in the adjacent salt marsh habitat and expose them to predation if they were flushed from cover or prevented from seeking available cover. If SMHM were present within the project area, they could be physically harmed, injured or killed if an individual were to come in contact with construction equipment or through actions of construction personnel. The SMHM is only likely to use the project area during high tide events and the project proposes to only conduct construction activities during low tide. No work is planned to occur in the adjacent salt marsh habitat and any SMHM near construction activities should be able to find sufficient cover within the tidal marsh. The project proposes to utilize a Service-approved biological monitor, environmental awareness training for construction personnel and additional conservation measures that further reduce the risk of harming, injuring or killing a SMHM. The project is proposed to take approximately 6 to 8 months in duration. It is anticipated that SMHM would be able to withstand the level of disturbance in relation to the nearby urban background environment. SMHM are mostly nocturnal and are not likely to be active during the day which reduces their exposure to adverse effects from construction activities. The project will result in the permanent loss of 0.03 acre of salt marsh habitat for SMHM. The habitat identified to be lost is of poor quality and it is not likely that SMHM would utilize the affected habitat with the exception of high water refugia.

Cumulative Effects

Cumulative effects include the effects of future State, Tribal, local or private actions that are reasonably certain to occur in the action area considered in this biological opinion. Future Federal actions unrelated to the proposed project are not considered in this section, because they require separate consultation pursuant to section 7 of the Act. The Service is not aware of specific projects that might affect the CCR and SMHM in the action area that are currently under review by State, county, or local authorities or are reasonably certain to occur.

Conclusion

After reviewing the current status of the CCR and SMHM, the environmental baseline for the action area, the effects of the proposed action, and the cumulative effects, it is the Service's biological opinion that the project, as proposed, is not likely to jeopardize the continued existence of the CCR and SMHM. This is based on the majority of the project being conducted on the developed paved uplands, in the small portions of riprapped shoreline and in ruderal vegetation. The habitat proposed to be permanently lost is considered marginal in relation to the surrounding Alviso salt marsh complex (which includes New Chicago Marsh) and is not expected to reduce the availability of higher quality habitat nearby or reduce the survivability of CCR and SMHM within the larger Alviso salt marsh complex. This is also based on the small scope and duration of construction activities and implementation of conservation measures.

INCIDENTAL TAKE STATEMENT

Section 9 of the Act and Federal regulation pursuant to section 4(d) of the Act prohibit the take of endangered and threatened species, respectively, without special exemption. Take is defined as harass, harm, pursue, hunt, shoot, wound, kill, trap, capture or collect, or to attempt to engage in any such conduct. Harass is defined by the Service as an intentional or negligent act or omission which creates the likelihood of injury to a listed species by annoying it to such an extent as to significantly disrupt normal behavioral patterns which include, but are not limited to, breeding, feeding or sheltering. Harm is defined by the Service to include significant habitat modification or degradation that results in death or injury to listed species by significantly impairing essential behavioral patterns including breeding, feeding, or sheltering. Incidental take is defined as take that is incidental to, and not the purpose of, the carrying out of an otherwise lawful activity. Under the terms of section 7(b)(4) and section 7(o)(2), taking incidental to and not intended as part of the agency action is not considered to be prohibited taking under the Act, provided that such taking is in compliance with the terms and conditions of this Incidental Take Statement.

The measures described below are non-discretionary, and must be undertaken by the Corps and the City so that they become binding conditions of any grant or permit issued to the applicants, as appropriate, for the exemption in section 7(o)(2) to apply. The Corps and the City have a continuing duty to regulate the activity covered by this incidental take statement. If the Corps (1) fail to assume and implement the terms and conditions or (2) fails to require the applicant to adhere to the terms and conditions of the incidental take statement through enforceable terms that are added to the permit or grant document, the protective coverage of section 7(o)(2) may lapse. In order to monitor the impact of incidental take, the Corps and the City must report the progress of the action and its impact on the species to the Service as specified in the incidental take statement [50 CFR §402.14(i)(3)].

Amount or Extent of Take

Conservation measures proposed by the City and described in the "Description of the Proposed Action" above will reduce but may not eliminate the potential for incidental taking of CCR and SMHM. The Service considers the number of CCR and SMHM subject to harassment from noise and vibrations, and human activities to be impracticable to estimate. The Service, therefore, anticipates the following levels of take as a result of implementation of the proposed action.

1. Harassment of all CCR and SMHM in the adjacent Alviso Slough and New Chicago Marsh habitats within 700 feet of the project construction areas.

Upon implementation of the reasonable and prudent measures, incidental take associated with the project will become exempt from the prohibitions described under section 9 of the Act.

Effect of the Take

In the accompanying biological opinion, the Service determines that the levels of take are not likely to result in jeopardy to the CCR and SMHM.

Reasonable and Prudent Measures

The following reasonable and prudent measure is necessary and appropriate to minimize the effects of the proposed project to the CCR and SMHM:

1. The Corps through the City and its contractors will minimize the potential for harassment of CCR and SMHM.

Terms and Conditions

In order to be exempt from the prohibitions of section 9 of the Act, the Corps shall ensure that the City complies with the following term and condition, which implement their respective reasonable and prudent measure described above. This term and condition is non-discretionary.

Implement the proposed action along with the proposed conservation measures as described in this biological opinion.

Reporting Requirements

In order to monitor whether the amount or extent of incidental take anticipated from implementation of the project is approached or exceeded, the Corps and the City shall adhere to the following reporting requirements. Should this anticipated amount or extent of incidental take be exceeded, the Corps must reinitiate formal consultation as per 50 CFR 402.16.

1. The Service must be notified within 24 hours of the finding of any injured or dead listed species or any unanticipated damage to its habitat associated with the proposed project. Injured listed species shall be cared for by a licensed veterinarian or other qualified person, such as the Service-approved biologist for the proposed project. Notification will be made to the Service, and must include the date, time, and precise location of the individual/incident clearly indicated on a U.S. Geological Survey 7.5 minute quadrangle or other maps at a finer scale, as requested by the Service, and any other pertinent information. When an injured or dead individual of the listed species is found, the Corps and the City shall follow the steps outlined in the *Disposition of Individuals Taken* section below.
2. Sightings of any listed or sensitive animal species shall be reported to the Service and CNDDDB (<https://www.wildlife.ca.gov/Data/CNDDDB>).
3. The applicant shall submit a post-construction compliance report prepared by the on-site biologist to the San Francisco Bay-Delta Fish and Wildlife Office within sixty (60) calendar days of the date of the completion of construction activities. This report shall detail: (1) dates that construction occurred; (2) pertinent information concerning the success of the project in meeting the avoidance and minimization measures; (3) an explanation of failure to meet such measures, if any; (4) known project effects on the CCR and SMHM, if any; (5) occurrences of incidental take of these listed species, if any;

(6) documentation of employee environmental education; and (7) other pertinent information.

Disposition of Individuals Taken

Injured listed species must be cared for by a licensed veterinarian or other qualified person(s), such as the Service-approved biologist. Dead individuals must be sealed in a resealable plastic bag containing a paper with the date and time when the animal was found, the location where it was found, and the name of the person who found it, and the bag containing the specimen frozen in a freezer located in a secure site, until instructions are received from the Service regarding the disposition of the dead specimen. The Service contact persons are the Assistant Field Supervisor of the Endangered Species Division at (916) 930-5603; and the Resident Agent-in-Charge of the Service's Office of Law Enforcement, 5622 Price Way, McClellan, California 95562, at (916) 569-8444.

REINITIATION – CLOSING STATEMENT

This concludes formal consultation for the Alviso Pump Station Project. As provided in 50 CFR §402.16, reinitiation of formal consultation is required where discretionary Federal agency involvement or control over the action has been retained (or is authorized by law) and if: (1) the amount or extent of incidental take is exceeded; (2) new information reveals effects of the agency action that may affect listed species or critical habitat in a manner or to an extent not considered in this opinion; (3) the agency action is subsequently modified in a manner that causes an effect to the listed species or critical habitat not considered in this opinion; or (4) a new species is listed or critical habitat designated that may be affected by the action. In instances where the amount or extent of incidental take is exceeded, any additional take will not be exempt from the prohibitions of section 9 of the Act, pending reinitiation.

Please address any questions or concerns regarding this response to Brian Hansen, Endangered Species Biologist, at Brian_Hansen@fws.gov or (916) 930-5642 or Kim Squires, Section 7 Coordinator, at Kim_Squires@fws.gov. Please refer to Service file number 08FBDT00-2017-F-0024 in any future correspondence regarding this project.

Sincerely,

Kaylee Allen
Field Supervisor

LITERATURE CITED

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